

AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF RABI SORGHUM PRODUCTION IN BULDHANA DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study entitled "An Economic analysis of rabi sorghum production in Buldhana District" was conducted in the year 2023-24. Data for the selected study were collected with the aid of well-structured questionnaire. Data collected were analysed using the tabulation method along with the required statistical tool. The per hectare total cost of cultivation of sorghum i. e. cost 'C₃' was highest in small farmers i.e. Rs. 64808.70 followed by medium size group Rs. 59120.88 and in large size group Rs. 51309.03. The study revealed that, the input-output ratio at cost "C₃" was highest in large, medium and small farmers i.e. 1.37, 1.25, 1.22 respectively.

Keywords: Sorghum, Cost of cultivation, Cost and Returns, Input-Output ratio.

Introduction

Sorghum is the world's fifth-most important crop after rice, wheat, maize and barley. It is scientifically known as Sorghum bicolor L. belongs to Gramineae family and is popularly known as 'Jowar' in India. Among other millets, a large size is referred to as a 'Great millet'. It is also known as the "King of Millets". Sorghum is a major and important food grain in our country. Sorghum is the best alternative for extreme weather conditions and well suited to drought-prone regions. It is also called as Camel crop.

Area, production and yield of rabi sorghum in India was 3.04 million hectare, 2.63 million tonnes and 886 kg/ha, respectively. Among the states, Maharashtra stood first in area, production and yield of sorghum in (2023-24) was 16 lakh hectare, 14.04 lakh tones and 878 kg/ha, respectively. The area, production and productivity of rabi sorghum in Buldhana district (2023-24) was 232.55 hundred hectare, 250.42 tonnes, 1076.84 kg/ha, respectively.

Materials and Method:**Collection of Data**

The primary data was collected by survey method for the year 2023-24 with the help of specially designed questionnaire. The data was collected by conducting personal interviews with the sample growers. Potential 90 Sorghum grower was selected from Buldhana district. The data pertaining for the year 2023-24.

Selection of Villages

Three villages from each tahsil were selected randomly. Taroda, Sahastramuli and Shirwa villages from Motala tahsil and Tarapur, Borkhed and Warwand from Buldhana tahsil was selected.

Selection of Sorghum Growers

15 samples of rabi sorghum cultivators were randomly selected from each village. Thus, the total 90 rabi Sorghum cultivators from two tahsils were selected for the present study.

Cost concept

Economics of Sorghum production was work out by using standard cost concept. i.e. A₁, A₂, B₁, B₂, C₁, C₂, C₃.

Cost A₁ = All actual expenses in cash and kind incurred in production by the producer. The following item are included in cost A₁.

- Value of hired human labour
- Value of hired bullock labour
- Value of owned bullock labour
- Value of hired machine labour
- Value of owned machine labour
- Value of seeds
- Value of manure
- Value of fertilizer
- Value of irrigation
- Value of plant protection measures adopted
- Depreciation charges
- Land revenue and other taxes
- Miscellaneous charges

14. Repairing charges

15. Incidental charges

16. Interest on working capital @ 6 per cent annum

COST A₂=Cost A₁+ Rent paid for leased-in land**COST B₁**=Cost A₂+ Intertest value of owned fixed capital assets (excluding land)**COST B₂** =Cost B₁+Rental value of owned land (net land revenue) + rent paid for leased-in land**COST C₁**=Cost B₁+ Imputed value of family labour**COST C₂**=Cost B₂ + Imputed value of family labour**COST C₃**=Cost C₂ + 10 per cent of Cost 'C₂'**Cost of production per quintal**

Cost of production per quintal of selected rabi sorghum has been worked out by total cost minus value of by produce dividing by main product in quintal.

Gross Returns: Returns obtained from the sale of crop output i.e., main products and by products.

Net Returns: Net returns was computed at different standard cost concepts. i.e., Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, Cost C₃ by deducting from the gross returns.

Input-Output Ratio

This is the ratio which represents returns obtained per rupee of investment. It worked out by dividing returns by the respective cost. The input-output ratio was worked out on the basis of standard cost concepts. i.e., Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, Cost C₃ by deducting from the gross returns.

Results and Discussion**Cost of Cultivation of Rabi Sorghum Farmers**

The per hectare cost of rabi sorghum cultivation was determined for various size groups and the overall level is shown in Table 5.2.1. The table shows the average utilized input by the rabi sorghum farmers like human labour, bullock labour, machine labour, seed, manure, fertilizer. It also reveals the average charges like plant protection charges, incidental charges and repairs. Other than that, it shows the computed working capital, interest on working capital, depreciation on farm implements, land revenue and taxes, cost A, rental value of land, Interest on fixed capital, cost B and cost C. The average main produce, by produce, family labour, per quintal cost and gross value are presented in the given table below.

According to the table, the total per hectare cost of rabi sorghum cultivation, i.e. cost 'C₃,' was calculated to be 58285.63 at the overall level. The per hectare cost of cultivation of rabi sorghum in small, medium and large was estimated to Rs. 64808.70, 59120.880 and Rs. 51309.03, respectively. The per hectare output (yield) obtained was 27.02, 25.44 and 24.66 quintals in small, medium and large, respectively with an average of 25.63 quintals per hectare at overall level. This has resulted into gross returns of Rs. 79204.14, Rs. 73768.28 and Rs. 70204.68 per hectare in small, medium and large, respectively with average gross return of Rs 74148.66 per hectare at

overall level. The share of cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' at overall level to the total cost of rabi sorghum cultivation was 51.39 per cent and 51.39 per cent, respectively. The share of cost 'B₁' and cost 'B₂' to the total cost of rabi sorghum cultivation at overall level was 65.34 per cent and 86.42 per cent, respectively.

The primary items of cost 'A₁' at overall level were hired human labor (16.25%) and machine power (7.33%), while the major items of cost 'B₁' was rental value of the land being owned (21.08%). Manure, fertilizer and plant protection expenditures comprised 1.99 per cent, 3.11 per cent and 0.44 per cent of the overall cost of rabi sorghum cultivation, respectively. The bullock labour and seed comprised 2.51 and 2.35 percent of the cost of sorghum cultivation, respectively.

Cost and returns from Rabi Sorghum

Studies on economics of production of sorghum help to understand the profitability and selection of appropriate crop on the farm. The data on cost and returns from sorghum is presented in the following table 2.

It could be revealed from the above table 5.2.2 that the gross return from sorghum production for overall average size group was Rs. 74148.66 per ha. The gross return from large size group was Rs. 70204.68, from medium size group Rs. 73768.27 and from small size group in Rs. 79204.13. The cost A₁, A₂, B₁, B₂, C₁, C₂, C₃ for overall farmer was Rs. 29952.23, Rs. 29952.23, Rs.38083.61, Rs. 50369.05, Rs. 40701.50, Rs. 52986.94 and Rs. 58285.63, respectively. Profit at cost "A₁" for overall size group from sorghum cultivation was Rs. 44196.43, at cost "A₂" Rs. 44196.43, at cost "B₁" Rs. 36065.05, at cost "B₂" Rs. 23779.61, at cost "C₁" Rs. 33447.17, at cost "C₂" Rs. 21161.73, at cost "C₃" Rs. 15863.03 respectively. The table also revealed that, the input-output ratio at overall level i.e.at cost "A₁", "A₂", "B₁", "B₂", "C₁", "C₂", "C₃" was 2.48, 2.48, 1.96, 1.48, 1.83, 1.41 and 1.28 respectively.

Conclusion

The per hectare total cost of cultivation of sorghum i. e. cost 'C₃' was highest in small farmers i.e. Rs. 64808.70 followed by medium size group Rs. 59120.88 and in large size group Rs. 51309.03. At the overall level it was Rs. 58285.63. The per hectare gross returns from sorghum at overall level was Rs. 74148.66. Profit at cost 'A₁' for overall size group from sorghum cultivation was Rs. 44196.43, at cost 'A₂' Rs. 44196.43, at cost 'B₁' Rs. 36065.05, at cost 'B₂' Rs. 23779.61, at cost 'C₁' Rs. 33447.17, at cost 'C₂' Rs. 21161.73, at cost 'C₃' Rs. 15863.03 respectively.

The study revealed that, the input-output ratio at cost "C₃" was highest in large, medium and small farmers i.e. 1.37, 1.25, 1.22 respectively.

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Table 1. Per Hectare cost of cultivation of Rabi Sorghum Farmers (Rs/ha)

Sr. No	Cost Items	Qty	Small		Medium		Large		Overall	
			Input /ha	Total cost per ha.						
1	Hired Human labour									
	a) Male	days	11.05	3554.90	11.37	3580.42	11.82	3849.38	11.42	3654.82
	b) Female	days	25.68	5768.98	23.86	5396.02	23.10	6464.30	24.12	5818.63
	Total human labour			9323.88		8976.44		10313.67		9473.45
2	Bullock power									0.00
	a) Owned	pair days	1.76	754.32	1.71	688.46	0.95	338.25	1.49	600.33
	b) Hired	pair days	2.35	1155.10	1.85	981.93	1.04	426.42	1.74	860.55
	Total bullock power			1909.42		1670.39		764.67		1460.88
3	Machine									0.00
	a) Owned	Hrs	3.33	1611.27	4.22	2188.77	2.41	1235.18	3.44	1745.98
	b) Hired	Hrs	6.01	3376.43	3.78	2271.02	3.71	2132.12	4.36	2525.30
	Total machine hrs			4987.70		4459.79		3367.30		4271.28
4	Manures	Qtls	6.92	1123.59	8.23	1336.72	5.75	932.99	7.13	1157.66
5	Seed	Kg	7.64	1502.61	7.80	1225.43	8.12	1448.11	7.85	1366.97
6	Fertilizers			1868.78		1788.93		1792.58		1811.43
	N	Kg	31.06	399.13	34.24	439.96	34.01	436.99	33.32	428.12
	P	Kg	40.66	1138.43	39.59	1108.51	35.95	436.99	38.78	913.70
	K	Kg	12.42	331.22	9.02	240.45	13.08	348.92	11.16	297.54
7	Irrigation Charges	Rs		-		-		-		-
8	Plant protection charges	Rs		196.55		265.85		300.00		257.59
9	Incidental charges	Rs		209.51		208.50		200.00		206.20
10	Repairs	Rs		440.89		441.50		440.32		440.98
11	Working capital	Rs		21562.93		20373.54		19559.64		20446.45
12	Interest on Working Capital @ 6 %	Rs		1293.78		1222.41		1173.58		1226.79
13	Depreciation on farm implements	Rs		4057.27		3575.58		1967.46		3218.95
14	Land revenue and taxes	Rs		114.89		57.66		56.58		72.67
15	Harvesting	Rs	27.03	5203.65	25.45	5003.05	24.66	4773.20	25.63	4987.38
	Cost 'A'	Rs		32232.52		30232.24		27530.45		29952.23
16	Rental value of leased land	Rs		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00
	Cost 'A ² '	Rs		32232.52		30232.24		27530.45		29952.23
17	Interest on fixed capital @ 10 %	Rs		10324.00		8744.46		5313.22		8131.38
	Cost 'B'	Rs		42556.52		38976.70		32843.68		38083.61
18	Rental value of land	Rs		13085.80		12237.06		11644.20		12285.44
	Cost 'B ² '	Rs		55642.32		51213.76		44487.88		50369.05
19	Family labour									
	a) Male	days	6.39	1550.99	5.30	1375.91	5.15	1342.87	5.54	1412.85
	b) Female	days	7.98	1723.69	5.50	1156.58	3.79	813.82	5.65	1205.03

	Sub Total			3274.68		2532.49		2156.69		2617.88
20	Cost 'C ¹ '	Rs		45831.20		41509.20		35000.37		40701.50
21	Cost 'C ² '	Rs		58917.00		53746.25		46644.57		52986.94
22	10% of C ²			5891.70		5374.63		4664.46		5298.69
23	Cost 'C ³ '	Rs		64808.70		59120.88		51309.03		58285.63
24	Yield									
	a. Main Produce	Qtls	27.03	70962.85	25.45	66843.52	24.66	65839.84	25.63	67644.30
	b. By-produce	Qtls	30.11	8241.28	24.23	6924.76	20.77	4364.85	24.76	6504.37
25	Gross Income			79204.14		73768.28		70204.68		74148.66
26	Per quintal cost	Rs		2092.89		2051.19		1903.63		2020.10

Table 2: cost and returns of Rabi Sorghum (Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Main Produce (Qtls)	27.03	25.45	24.66	25.63
	Price of Main Produce (Rs)	70962.85	66843.52	65839.83	67644.30
2	By Produce (Qtls)	30.11	24.23	20.77	24.76
	Price of By Produce (Rs)	8241.28	6924.75	4364.84	6504.37
3	Gross Income	79204.13	73768.27	70204.68	74148.66
4	Total Cost (Rs)				
	i) Cost 'A ₁ '	32232.51	30232.24	27530.45	29952.23
	ii) Cost 'A ₂ '	32232.51	30232.24	27530.45	29952.23
	iii) Cost 'B ₁ '	42556.51	38976.70	32843.67	38083.61
	iv) Cost 'B ₂ '	55642.31	51213.76	44487.88	50369.05
	v) Cost 'C ₁ '	45831.20	41509.19	35000.37	40701.50
	vi) Cost 'C ₂ '	58917.00	53746.25	46644.57	52986.94
	vii) Cost 'C ₃ '	64808.70	59120.88	51309.03	58285.63
5	Net Returns (Rs)				
	i) Cost 'A ₁ '	46971.62	43536.03	42674.23	44196.43
	ii) Cost 'A ₂ '	46971.62	43536.03	42674.23	44196.43
	iii) Cost 'B ₁ '	36647.61	34791.57	37361.00	36065.05
	iv) Cost 'B ₂ '	23561.82	22554.51	25716.80	23779.61
	v) Cost 'C ₁ '	33372.93	32259.08	35204.31	33447.17
	vi) Cost 'C ₂ '	20287.13	20022.02	23560.11	21161.73
	vii) Cost 'C ₃ '	14395.43	14647.39	18895.65	15863.03
6	Input-Output Ratio at				
	i) Cost 'A ₁ '	2.46	2.44	2.55	2.48
	ii) Cost 'A ₂ '	2.46	2.44	2.55	2.48
	iii) Cost 'B ₁ '	1.86	1.89	2.14	1.96
	iv) Cost 'B ₂ '	1.42	1.44	1.58	1.48
	v) Cost 'C ₁ '	1.73	1.78	2.01	1.83
	vi) Cost 'C ₂ '	1.34	1.37	1.51	1.41
	vii) Cost 'C ₃ '	1.22	1.25	1.37	1.28